

Supporting Information

Visible-light photo-iniferter polymerization of molecularly imprinted polymers for direct integration with nanotransducers

Tiziano Di Giulio¹, Ibrar Muhammad Asif¹, Martina Corsi², Giuseppe Egidio De Benedetto³ Cosimino Malitesta¹, Karsten Haupt^{4,5}, Giuseppe Barillaro^{2,*}, Carlo Gonzato^{4,*}, Elisabetta Mazzotta^{1,*}

¹Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry, Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences and Technologies (Di.S.Te.B.A.), University of Salento, via Monteroni, 73100 Lecce (Italy)

²Information Engineering Department, University of Pisa, via G. Caruso 16, 56122 Pisa (Italy)

³Laboratory of Analytical Mass Spectrometry, Cultural Heritage Department, University of Salento, Via Monteroni, 73100 Lecce (Italy)

⁴CNRS Enzyme and Cell Engineering Laboratory, Université de Technologie de Compiègne, Rue du Docteur Schweitzer, CS 60319, Compiègne 60203 (France)

⁵Institut Universitaire de France

giuseppe.barillaro@unipi.it; carlo.gonzato@utc.fr; elisabetta.mazzotta@unisalento.it.

Figure S1. a) Schematic of the setup used for reflectance measurements, featuring a halogen lamp as the light source and a UV-Vis spectrometer. b) Illustrative graph of reflectance spectra used to calculate EOT values, which serve as a parameter for the functionalization steps and for monitoring binding and removal events in the MIP sensor. Created in <https://BioRender.com>

Figure S2. Optical characterization of PSiO₂ scaffold during photo-iniferter polymerization for polymer deposition. Reflectance spectra recorded in air on a PSiO₂ scaffold before and after each functionalization step up to the polymer deposition.

Figure S3. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy characterization of PSiO₂ scaffolds upon photo-initiated polymerization. Survey scan recorded on a) bare PSiO₂ scaffold; b) after APTES silanization; c) after CDTPA grafting and d) after the polymer deposition (5 hours polymerization).

Figure S4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy characterization of PSiO₂ silanized with APTES. N1s (a) and C 1s (b) signals recorded after PSiO₂ silanization with APTES.

Figure S5. Relative atomic ratio calculated from XPS data. N/Si (a) and C/Si (b) ratio calculated for each functionalization step of P_{Si}O₂ samples for poly(MAA-co-EGDMA) deposition.

Figure S6. Contact angle measurements on Si wafer slides. a) contact angle recorded during the functionalized steps up to the polymer deposition. b) average contact angle values recorded for each functionalization step and after photo-iniferter polymerizations performed at different times (n=3). Data are presented as mean (\pm s.d).

Figure S7. Optical characterization of P_{SiO}₂ scaffold after polymer deposition for different polymerization times. Reflectance spectra recorded in air on a P_{SiO}₂ scaffold before and after photo-initiated polymerization for different times.

Figure S8. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy characterization of the polymer obtained by photo-iniferter polymerization. High-resolution C1s signal recorded after polymerization of poly(MAA-co-EDGMA) on PSiO₂ (a) and in solution as a bulk polymer (b).

Figure S9. Top-view SEM images and characterization of PSiO₂ scaffolds after deposition of MIP and NIP for 5 hours. Distribution of the pore diameters was obtained from the analysis of top-view SEM images using the “Equivalent Disc Radius” function in the Grain Distribution tool of the Gwyddion software. Scalebar: 200 nm.

Figure S10. MIP kinetic studies. Sensor response ($EOT-EOT_0$ versus propranolol concentration) recorded after the incubation of MIP-functionalized $PSiO_2$ scaffolds for different contact times, namely 5, 10, 20, 30, 45 and 60 minutes; EOT_0 is the signal recorded for the blank solution and used as reference. Propranolol concentration: 0.05 mM. MIP polymerization time: 5 hours.

Figure S11: MIP characterization by Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectra of bare PSiO_2 (dark line), NIP-coated (blue line) and MIP-coated (red line) PSiO_2 scaffolds recorded from 100 to 1800 cm^{-1} . As control, a Raman spectrum of a bulk polymer was also recorded (green line) The bulk polymer was obtained using the same method but with the photo-iniferter (at 1% of the total concentration of monomer and crosslinker) in the polymerization mixture.

Figure S12. Detection tests using MIPs- and NIPs-based sensors. Reflectance spectra recorded in air on a) PSiO₂ scaffold functionalized with MIP for propranolol after exposure to different concentrations of propranolol. b) NIP-coated PSiO₂ sample after exposure to different concentrations of propranolol. c) PSiO₂ scaffold functionalized with MIP for atenolol after exposure to different concentrations of atenolol.

Figure S13. MIP-based sensor performance in propranolol and atenolol detection. a) Calibration curves (EOT-EOT₀) recorded using propranolol-imprinted polymers for propranolol (black dots) and atenolol (orange dots) detection. b) Calibration curves (EOT-EOT₀) recorded using atenolol-imprinted polymers for propranolol (black dots) and atenolol (orange dots) detection